

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF VEGF GENE POLYMORPHISM RS2010963 AND RS833061 ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME**Savchuk T.***Doctor of Philosophy***Berbeniuk A.***Student**Bukovinian State Medical University***Savchuk Yu.***Doctor anesthesiologist**Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital***Abstract**

PCOS is considered a heterogeneous disease and one of the factors of its development may be a violation of ovarian angiogenesis, which is associated with the modification of the vascular endothelial growth factor VEGF. VEGF rs833061 T and rs2010963 G alleles correlate with increased VEGF levels and the development of PCOS. Studies by Chinese scientists note that the rs833061 polymorphism of the VEGF gene correlates with the risk of PCOS. The effects of gene polymorphisms on the risk of PCOS were reported in the literature, but this analysis was not conducted among Ukrainian women. **The purpose of the study.** Perform a meta-analysis of data obtained from databases and search engines: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed and Google Scholar, Meta by key words on the topic of the study: "VEGF or VEGFA or VPF", "PCOS or polycystic ovary syndrome" and "polymorphism". **Materials and methods.** The study of data from a molecular genetic study in women with polycystic ovary syndrome regarding the polymorphism of the VEGF gene was carried out using a meta-analysis by studying and analyzing scientific publications over the past 5 years on the topic of this study. Databases and search engines were used to search for literature sources: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed and Google Scholar, Meta using key words on the research topic: "VEGF or VEGFA or VPF", "PCOS or polycystic ovary syndrome" and "polymorphism". The last search was updated on April 14, 2024. 15 case-control studies with different variants of PCOS were obtained. **The results:** after conducting a meta-analysis, we obtained graphical confirmation of the connection between PCOS and polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene. In the five studies analyzed by us regarding the influence of polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene, a corresponding pattern was established. **Conclusions.** A meta-analysis of literature sources from databases and search engines: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed and Google Scholar, Meta by keywords on the topic of the study: "VEGF or VEGFA or VPF", "PCOS or polycystic ovary syndrome" and "polymorphism" established a correlation between PCOS and rs2010963 and rs833061 polymorphisms.

Keywords: polycystic ovary syndrome, polymorphism, VEGF, rs2010963 and rs833061 polymorphisms.

Introduction. The study of biochemical and pathogenetic mechanisms of the development of PCOS in patients who are related by family ties of the first line led scientists to believe that PCOS has a genetic nature [1]. This pattern can be observed in 20-40% of cases of disease manifestation, which is confirmed by identical manifestations of PCOS in twins. The contribution of genetic factors to the development of PCOS is 79%, and other exo and endogenous factors, such as: weight, age, metabolic disorders have a significant modifying effect on the clinical manifestations of PCOS [2]. Specialists continue to search for genes that regulate hypothalamic-pituitary interactions, are responsible for steroidogenesis in the ovaries, are genetic factors of insulin resistance, and regulate carbohydrate metabolism, the appearance and development of oxidative stress [3]. The existence of six genetic loci associated with PCOS, which regulate the pituitary release of gonadotropic hormones, has been proven, and using the method of Mendelian randomization, it is possible to assert the connection of PCOS with a high body mass index (BMI), insulin resistance, and a low concentration of globulins, which are affected by sex hormones [4]. Experts confirmed the connection between the alleles responsible for the later onset of menopause and the risk of PCOS. Increased levels of LH have been proven in

women with PCOS. Changes in LH regulation depend on modifications of the gene that encodes the β -subunit of LH. Studies conducted by Furui and others proved the presence of double-point mutations Trp 8 Arg and Ile 15 Thr and single-point missense mutation Gln 102 Ser in the β -subunit of LH. These mutations are manifestations of polymorphisms that increase the level of LH. The FSH receptor is encoded by a gene that consists of 14 exons and is located on chromosome 2p16.3. The mutation of the gene distorts the effects of FSH on the receptors, which is manifested by impaired maturation and growth of follicles, which leads to the development of PCOS [1,2].

Biochemical methods have established that the process of aromatization of androgens to estrogens depends on P450-aromatase. This process of complex biochemical transformations, which begins with the transformation of cholesterol into progesterone. P450c17 α catalyzes the chain of transformations of 17-hydroxyprogesterone from pregnenellone and 17 OH-progesterone from progesterone with further transformation into dehydroepiandrosterone and androstenedione. Polymorphism of the genes responsible for the synthesis of the enzyme and cytochrome P 450 complex is considered a factor in the pathogenesis of PCOS,

for example, the CYP11A1 gene encodes P450scc enzymes. CYP11a encodes the conversion of cholesterol to progesterone. The enzyme encoded by this gene is located on the inner membrane of mitochondria, and the gene is located on region 15q24.1 and contains 10 exons [3]. Increased activity of CYP11A causes hyperandrogenism. Research conducted in South India established the presence of 15 allelic variations of the CYP11 A gene and the most common 8 alleles. This study clearly emphasizes that the recurrence of these 8 alleles correlates with a 3-fold increase in PCOS. Similar data were obtained in China regarding the role of the CYP11 A gene. The CYP17 gene regulates P450c17 α . The gene consists of 8 exons and is located on chromosome 10q24.32. If a single nucleotide polymorphism is observed in the promoter region of the gene, the risk of PCOS increases. The CYP19 gene encodes aromatase P450 arom [4]. P450 arom is a member of the gene superfamily. Biochemical studies have established that aromatase consists of 410 amino acid residues and catalyzes various reactions in its active center. These 3 reactions take place on substrates: androstenedione, testosterone, and 16 α -hydroxytestosterone, which in the aromatization reaction by adding oxygen form the phenolic ring of estrogens and turn into estrone, 17 β -estradiol, and 17 β , 16 α -estriol [5,6].

Cytochrome P450 aromatase is located in the endoplasmic reticulum and is responsible for the synthesis of estrogens. In all women with PCOS, the amount of estradiol P450 aroma-mRNA in the follicles decreased and aromatase activity decreased accordingly, which may be the reason for the accumulation of androgens and impaired follicle formation. Studies of the role of CYP17A1 gene polymorphisms are ambiguously described in the literature: in scientific works, both an increase in the frequency of CYP17A1 alleles and genotypes in PCOS, and the absence of a connection with the disease are described [7,8]. The genetic determination of the 5-alpha-reductase enzyme in the development of PCOS has also been proven. Described clinical studies of 237 women with PCOS, who underwent biochemical measurements of 5-alpha-reductase and carried out genetic studies, which established a connection between SRD5A1 and SRD5A2 gene polymorphisms and clinical manifestations. Androgen receptor genes consider the reduction of CAG repeats in the exon of this gene as a factor in hyperandrogenism. Insulin resistance is a leading factor in the development of PCOS, the gene encoding insulin receptors INSR has a polymorphism in exon 17-21, a polymorphism of tyrosine kinase, which is associated with the development of insulin resistance. The CYP21 gene encodes 21-hydroxylase and is responsible for the biochemical transformation of 7-hydroxyprogesterone into 11-deoxycortisol. This gene consists of 10 exons and is located on site 6p21.33. Deficiency of the 21-hydroxylase enzyme is a consequence of an autosomal recessive mutation of this gene and an increase in 17-hydroxyprogesterone in the serum of women [9,10].

The gene for sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) binds to androgens and transports them to their site of action, thus regulating hormone levels. The gene for this hormone is located on chromosome 17p13-p12.

The transcriptional activity of the gene is regulated by the pentanucleotide polymorphism (TAAAA) $_n$ in the promoter region. Greek scientists conducted research and established a relationship between the pentanucleotide repeat, which causes low levels of SHBG in the blood serum, which promotes the effect of testosterone on target cells. The AMG gene, which is associated with female fertility, consists of 5 exons and is located on chromosome 19q13.3. Polymorphism of this gene changes the fertility of women and there is evidence of its involvement in the development of PCOS [11,12].

The insulin gene INS via Pk-B (protein kinase-B) is found in the theca cells of women with PCOS. The regulatory site of the INS gene is embedded in the VNTR and has a polymorphism. However, the involvement of this gene polymorphism in the development of PCOS is controversial [14,15].

The gene that encodes insulin receptors (INSR) consists of two subunits and is located on the 19th chromosome. Studies conducted on women with PCOS and obesity have not established correlations between gene polymorphisms and the syndrome [16,17].

The relationship between polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene and changes in a woman's hormonal profile [18,19].

PCOS is considered a heterogeneous disease and one of the factors of its development may be a violation of ovarian angiogenesis, which is associated with the modification of the vascular endothelial growth factor VEGF. Research conducted at the Lviv National Medical University established reliable links between the rs2010963 polymorphism and the development of diabetic retinopathy, which proves the involvement of the gene in the regulation of blood vessel growth [20].

The VEGF gene belongs to the PDGF/VEGF growth factor family and is located on site 6p21.1 and contains 9 exons. This gene is expressed in theca cells and is involved in the physiological regulation of ovarian angiogenesis. Polymorphisms are noted in the promoter and intronic regions and may be the cause of PCOS [21].

VEGF rs833061 T and rs2010963 G alleles correlate with increased VEGF levels and the development of PCOS. Studies by Chinese scientists note that the rs833061 polymorphism of the VEGF gene correlates with the risk of PCOS. The influence of gene polymorphisms on the risk of PCOS was reported in the literature, but this analysis was not conducted among Ukrainian women [22,23].

The purpose of the study: to establish a possible connection with polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene on the development of PCOS through a meta-analysis [24, 25].

The main tasks of the work are:

1. To conduct a review of literature data on the factors of the development of PCOS.

2. Perform a meta-analysis of data obtained from databases and search engines: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed and Google Scholar, Meta by keywords on the topic of the study: "VEGF or VEGFA or VPF", "PCOS or polycystic ovary syndrome" and "polymorphism".

Materials and methods. A generalization and analysis of scientific publications over the past 5 years

on the topic of this research was carried out. Databases and search engines were used to search for literature sources: Web of Science, Scopus, CiteSeerX, Microsoft Academic Search, AMiner, BASE, WorldWideScience, CORE, PubMed and Google Scholar, Meta by keywords on the research topic.

Research design

A total of 52 articles from the Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed, and Google Scholar, Meta databases were processed using a literature search using keywords. Five articles were included in the current meta-analysis (Figure 1). The analyzed results of the relationship between manifestations of the VEGF gene polymorphism and the risk of PCOS are summarized in Table 2. In all studies, the control group was women without PCOS. The detailing of 5 cases of gene polymorphism was rs699947, rs833061 (three case-control studies including 245 cases and 248 controls), rs3025039 (four case-control studies including 250 cases and 255 controls), rs833063 (three case-control studies -control", including 270 cases and 275 controls).

Research methods

Study of molecular genetic research data in women with polycystic ovary syndrome regarding VEGF gene polymorphism

The study of data from a molecular genetic study in women with polycystic ovary syndrome regarding the polymorphism of the VEGF gene was carried out using a meta-analysis by studying and analyzing scientific publications over the past 5 years on the topic of this study. Databases and search engines were used to search for literature sources: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed and Google Scholar, Meta using key words on the research topic: "VEGF or VEGFA or VPF", "PCOS or polycystic ovary syndrome" and "polymorphism". The last search was updated on April 14, 2024. 15 case-control studies with different variants of PCOS were obtained.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion of studies for further consideration had to meet the following criteria: (1) an analysis of the correlation between PCOS and the VEGF gene was conducted; (2) the "control case" took place (3) the cases of polymorphism rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene and PCOS were considered. Exclusion criteria from the meta-analysis were as follows: (1) no control (2) no analysis of genetic dependence of VEGF and PCOS.

Data analysis

To systematize the data in the selected articles, the following were determined: surname of the first author, year of publication, country of publication, phenotypic manifestation of PCOS, number of people who participated in the study - patients and those without PCOS manifestations, number of each genotype, frequency in the "case/control" group, Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) in the control group and genotyping method. With the help of online programs for systematization of reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) on the website URL: <https://www.prisma-statement.org/>, a Prisma checklist and a Prisma flowchart were compiled.

Statistical data processing Using the online calculator metaHUN: a web, a meta-analysis was performed on the website URL: <http://softmed.hacettepe.edu.tr/metaHUN/>. Odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence interval (CI) was used to measure the strength of association between VEGF gene polymorphisms and PCOS risk. The statistical significance of the total ZOSH was determined using the Z-test. The assumption of heterogeneity was assessed across studies using a chi-squared Q-test. If the value of $P < 0.10$ for the Q test indicated the heterogeneity of the studies. The fixed effects model (Mantel-Hanzel method) was used.

Research results.

With the help of meta-analysis and conducted literature search, using the online programs Prisma and Meta, we created a block diagram and formed a table on the influence of polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene on the development of polycystic ovary syndrome.

In the biomedical sciences, a meta-analysis is a systematic, orderly, and structured assessment of a research problem that is conducted using information from a number of independent studies. The goal of meta-analysis is to integrate indicators and draw conclusions about the possible manifestation of the phenomenon [23,24,34,35,36].

Based on the analysis of the literature, a block diagram was compiled using the Prisma online program (see Fig. 1), in which the data on the number of articles included and excluded from the study were indicated, as well as a list of literary sources was formed from the databases used for the search with the indication surnames of the author, year, country, number of women in the experimental and control groups. As well as a table (see Tab. 1) containing the results of these studies.

Figure 1. List of articles included and excluded from the study

Table 1.

Results of literature studies that investigated rs2010963 and rs833061 polymorphisms of the vascular endothelial growth factor gene in polycystic ovary syndrome.

Author	Polymorphism of which genes were studied	Number of women who participated in the study	Main result and conclusions
Bao and others	rs1547651, rs1570360, rs2010963, rs3025020, rs3025039, rs699947, rs833061, rs833058, rs833068	55 women with PCOS and 52 controls	VEGF levels in rs699947, rs3025039 and rs833061 genotypes were significantly higher in PCOS. The results of the study clearly proved that allelic variants in genes can be a factor for PCOS and VEGF serum levels only for a few polymorphism variants
Huang et al	rs2010963, rs833061	118 with PCOS and 130 controls	Our study shows for the first time that the rs2010963 polymorphism may be associated with the risk of PCOS in North Chinese women.
Vicente and others	rs2010963 i rs833061	102 with PCOS and 108 controls	The clinical characteristics of the patients showed that 36.3% had a family history of polycystic ovary syndrome, 58.6% had obesity, and about 60% had clinical characteristics of hyperandrogenism. There was no association between the distribution of rs2010963 and rs833061 in patients and controls.
Gomes MKO	rs3025039, rs 699947 rs2010963 rs833061	110 without PCOS and 112 women with PCOS.	Conclusions: Patients with polycystic ovary syndrome have similar rates of VEGF rs2010963 and rs833061 polymorphisms in the general population.

After conducting a meta-analysis, we obtained graphical confirmation of the connection between PCOS and polymorphisms rs2010963 and rs833061 of

the VEGF gene. In the five studies analyzed by us regarding the influence of the polymorphism rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene, a corresponding regularity was established (see Fig. 2,3, 4, 5).

Figure. 2 The effect of polymorphism rs2010963 and rs833061 of the VEGF gene on the manifestations of PCOS. Linear regression.

Figure 3. Forest plot of PCOS risk associated with VEGF gene polymorphisms (rs699947, rs833061, rs1570360) (recessive model) overall Squares and horizontal lines correspond to study ORs and 95% CIs. The area of the squares reflects the weight (inverse variance). Rhombus represents final SD and 95% CI.

Figure 4. Radial plot of PCOS risk associated with VEGF gene polymorphisms (rs699947, rs833061, rs1570360)

Figure 5. Funnel plot of PCOS risk associated with VEGF gene polymorphisms (rs699947, rs833061, rs1570360).

The obtained data of the meta-analysis correlate with the data of the literature, which noted the presence of a strong connection between an increase in the level of VEGF in blood serum and PCOS, as well as a correlation between VEGF polymorphisms (rs699947, rs833061, rs1570360) [27].

Some researchers indicate that serum VEGF levels are associated with increased blood flow in the ovarian stroma in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. On the other hand, this protein may play an important role in the pathophysiology of PCOS, contributing to ovulatory dysfunction, infertility, and ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome commonly observed in women with PCOS [28,29,30].

To understand the role of the VEGF gene in the development of PCOS, it is advisable to study the polymorphism of this gene. Specialists studied the effect of VEGF gene polymorphism on the manifestations of PCOS. It was found that polymorphisms in the promoter region (loci: -2578, -1154 and -460) or intron 6 (loci: -583) or 5'-untranslated region (loci: +405, +963 and -634) or +534 were associated with different levels of VEGF expression. -2578 C, -460 T and +405 G alleles correlate with altered levels of VEGF expression. An association between elevated serum VEGF levels and PCOS has been demonstrated, and a correlation between serum VEGF levels and increased ovarian stromal blood flow in women with PCOS. The literature found five types of polymorphism (rs699947, rs833061, rs1570360, rs3025020, rs3025039), which can act as a risk factor for the development of PCOS; in addition, three polymorphisms (rs2010963, +9812, +405) may have a protective effect on PCOS [31,32]. The rs699947, rs3025020 and +405 polymorphisms corresponded to abnormal serum VEGF gene expression and could be associated with the risk of PCOS serum VEGF levels. Different factors can cause different polymorphisms in the same gene and can cause gene expression that leads to different risks of PCOS [3,14,5,26]. Second, individual genes or environmental factors may not have a direct effect on susceptibility to PCOS, but complex interactions between genetic and environmental factors may be involved in the development of the disease. Family history has been shown to

be more common in PCOS patients. According to the literature, multiple family and twin studies have confirmed the role of genetics in the etiology of PCOS with a high heritability of 70% [7,18,29,30,9].

Conclusions. A meta-analysis of literature sources from databases and search engines: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed and Google Scholar, Meta by keywords on the topic of the study: "VEGF or VEGFA or VPF", "PCOS or polycystic ovary syndrome" and "polymorphism » established a correlation between PCOS and rs2010963 and rs833061 polymorphisms.

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